
Snowy Owl Migratory Behavior and Management at DTW

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Purpose:

To assess snowy owl activity, migratory behavior, airfield use, and management at DTW to inform evidence-based wildlife hazard management.

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Preface

Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) is committed to maintaining the highest standards of aviation safety, security, and operational efficiency. In accordance with 14 CFR §139.337 and DTW's Wildlife Hazard Management Plan, proactively identifying and mitigating wildlife hazards is essential to reducing strike risk and protecting both airfield operations and the traveling public. Among these hazards, snowy owls (*Bubo scandiacus*) have emerged as an important problem. During winter migration, snowy owls periodically move through and perch near active runways at DTW, where they are at heightened risk of aircraft collisions—posing significant challenges to airfield safety and operations.

Recognizing the importance of this issue, the Wayne County Airport Authority (WCAA) Airfield Operations – Wildlife Division conducted a comprehensive, multi-year evaluation of snowy owl activity, migration behavior, and management at DTW. This assessment integrated multiple datasets and operational records to provide a full-scope understanding of snowy owl behavior and to identify practical, evidence-based strategies for reducing risk. The findings and recommendations presented here reinforce DTW's commitment to collaborative, science-driven, and adaptive wildlife hazard management, while supporting ongoing interdepartmental coordination to meet regulatory obligations and maintain operational integrity.

This report builds upon—and supplements—DTW's Wildlife Hazard Management Plan, with particular relevance to snowy owl and broader raptor management. It also contributes to the Wildlife Division's Special Publication Series, established to strengthen institutional memory, document applied research, and provide clear justification for management decisions. In doing so, this report offers value not only to DTW, but also to other airports facing similar wildlife–aircraft conflict challenges.

Management recommendations

- **Make snowy owl response a top-priority** task for Wildlife Division staff during winter migration, and reinforce its importance across all relevant airport departments.
- **Prepare early.** Assemble trapping equipment, lure birds , passive traps (e.g., Swedish goshawk traps), and monitoring tools (binoculars/FLIR), and complete staff training by early October.
- **Deploy passive traps at hotspot locations** by early October to support early-season captures and reduce reliance on reactive trapping.
- **Initiate early-season outreach.** Remind airport personnel of the importance of promptly reporting snowy owl sightings and provide clear instructions for contacting Wildlife staff.
- **Maintain rapid, reliable communication channels** (e.g., automatic email notifications, phone calls) among departments to support fast detection and response.
- **Ensure Wildlife Division coverage during peak activity periods**—particularly morning and evening crepuscular windows.
- **Survey known hotspot areas regularly** and share hotspot maps with relevant departments at the start of each migration season.
- **Continue targeted small-mammal management** in areas where prey availability exceeds operational thresholds.
- **Continue long-distance, habitat-based translocations** given their demonstrated reduction in snowy owl recapture rates.
- **Document all trapping events, sightings, and translocation outcomes** using standardized data entry methods to support adaptive management and long-term evaluation.
- **Conduct an annual end-of-season** review to assess performance, identify training needs, refine trapping protocols, and update operational priorities for the following migration period.

Regulatory compliance:

14 CFR Part 139

14 CFR Part 139, also known as the Airport Certification regulation, outlines the requirements for airports to obtain and maintain an operating certificate from the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA). This certification ensures that airports meet certain safety and emergency response standards. Airports like DTW that serve scheduled air carrier operations with aircraft seating more than 9 passengers—or at least 31 passengers for unscheduled operations—are required to be certified under 14 CFR Part 139.

14 CFR § 139.337

This section of Part 139 mandates wildlife hazard management to mitigate the risk of aircraft collisions with wildlife. Under this section, certificated airports are required to identify and mitigate wildlife hazards that pose a risk to air carrier operations. This approach includes monitoring wildlife activity, reducing attractants (e.g., standing water, cover, food sources), taking immediate action to disperse or remove hazardous wildlife when necessary, and adapting management strategies as needed. Airports certificated under Part 139 must have a Wildlife Hazard Management Plan as part of their Airport Certification Manual (Figure 1).

Airport Certification Manual

To comply with 14 CFR Part 139, airports must develop and maintain an Airport Certification Manual, which details procedures for meeting all 14 CFR Part 139 regulatory requirements. If wildlife hazards are identified (like they are at DTW), the ACM must include a Wildlife Hazard Management Plan. The Airport Certification Manual is a central component of the airport-certification process.

Wildlife Hazard Management Plan

The Wildlife Hazard Management Plan addresses the responsibilities, policies, and procedures necessary to reduce wildlife hazards. Specifically, airports must develop and implement a plan to manage wildlife hazards, including measures to reduce attractants (like standing water or food sources) and methods for actively dispersing or removing wildlife. Relevant to this report and recommendations therein, the Airport Certification Manual also designates WCAA departments responsible for implementing the plan, including Airfield Operations – Wildlife Division. The Wildlife Hazard Management Plan is a dynamic document that must be updated based on monitoring results and hazard assessments. It also assigns the WCAA Wildlife Biologists to evaluate wildlife trends and,

in coordination with USDA Wildlife Services, develop more detailed recommendations as problems are identified.

FAA Advisory Circular 150/5200-33

In compliance with 14 CFR § 139.337, the DTW Wildlife Hazard Management Plan was developed following FAA issued AC 150/5200-33 guidance (*Wildlife Hazard Management at Airports*). This federal guidance document supports development and implementation of Wildlife Hazard Management Plans and provides a framework for reducing wildlife hazards through active monitoring, habitat modification, exclusion, and interagency coordination.

Figure 1. Regulatory compliance overview regarding wildlife management at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW). To maintain an operating certificate from the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), DTW must implement a Wildlife Hazard Management Plan and appropriately respond to relevant, emerging wildlife issues.

Introduction

Raptors pose substantial hazards to aviation due to their large body size, low-altitude flight behavior, and use of open landscapes associated with airport environments. Because raptor movements often overlap with aircraft during critical phases of flight (e.g., takeoff and landing), they account for a disproportionate number of damaging wildlife–aircraft collisions in North America (also referred to as strikes; Dolbeer 2006). Airports further elevate this risk by providing extensive open, early-successional habitats that many raptors perceive as suitable hunting grounds, creating conditions consistent with ecological traps—habitats that appear favorable but expose animals to heightened mortality risk (Schlaepfer et al. 2002).

Snowy owls (*Bubo scandiacus*) are a notable example of a raptor highly susceptible to these conditions. Their large body mass (~2 kg), low flying behavior, and frequent use of low perches bring them into direct conflict with aircraft operations (Boxall & Lein 1982; Kerlinger & Lein 1988). Nationally, 394 snowy owl strikes have been reported to the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), including damaging events averaging \$278,284 per incident (95% CI: \$44,299–\$512,269; FAA NWSD 2025). To exacerbate this issue, strike risk increases during irruptive winters, when high reproductive output in the Arctic drives large southward movements of snowy owls into unfamiliar human-dominated landscapes (Robillard et al. 2016; Curk et al. 2018).

Airports may be particularly attractive to wintering snowy owls because their open terrain and prey availability resemble tundra-like foraging conditions (Baker & Brooks 1981). Once on airfields, snowy owls often perch on elevated structures and cross active runways, bringing their movements into direct overlap with aircraft operations and increasing both collision risk and management demands (McCabe et al. 2022). As a highly charismatic species with substantial public interest, their presence alone draws considerable attention, yet this same visibility heightens concern when snowy owls settle at airports. Strikes involving snowy owls therefore represent both a public-safety hazard—given their mass and flight behavior—and a conservation concern, as aircraft collisions contribute directly to mortality in a species already listed as Vulnerable under the IUCN Red List (McCabe et al. 2024). These intersecting risks further complicate management, particularly because lethal control is publicly unpopular for many species (Martínez-Espiñeira 2006; Buteau et al. 2022) and especially contentious for snowy owls.

Given these operational, ecological, and conservation considerations, airport-specific assessments of snowy owl activity and space use are essential for developing effective and publicly acceptable management strategies. Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) has historically experienced recurring snowy owl activity and strike

events, highlighting the need for a detailed local evaluation. The purpose of this study was to assess snowy owl records at DTW to support evidence-based wildlife hazard mitigation. Specifically, our objectives were to (1) characterize snowy owl activity, migratory behavior, and airfield use at DTW; and (2) evaluate historical management actions and outcomes to identify strategies that strengthen operational safety and provide recommendations.

Methods

Snowy owl data

We used data from multiple sources in this study, including in-house records from WCAA's Airfield Operations – Wildlife Division and strike report data from the FAA's National Wildlife Strike Database (retrieved 24 October 2025; NWSD 2025). WCAA records originated from two merged datasets that reflected improvements in data collection methods over time. These records included Historical Wildlife Activity data (collected approximately 2016–2022) and Survey123 Wildlife Activity data collected through a designated ArcGIS Survey123 application (beginning in 2022; data retrieved 14 October 2025). These Survey123 records contained more precise spatial information (e.g., coordinates), while older records provided only coarse location data by Wildlife Management Zone (n = 22). To maximize sample size, we incorporated the less explicit Historical Wildlife Activity data when appropriate. We also converted calendar years into biologically relevant migration periods, defined as September through August (e.g., migration period 2021–2022 spanned September 2021 through August 2022). We removed all records from the 2015–2016 period to ensure consistency with WCAA's standardized wildlife datasets, which begin with the 2016–2017 migration period. All subsequent analyses followed this September–August framework for consistent temporal comparison across years.

Capture-method assessment

We evaluated the use of different snowy owl capture methods using WCAA data. The dataset included 722 records of snowy owl observations, including successful captures—defined as events with outcomes that indicated the bird was relocated, taken to a rehabilitator, or was a foreign recapture (i.e., bird previously caught and banded elsewhere). For each capture method, we calculated the proportion of successful capture events and visualized the results to compare relative method use.

Time-of-day analysis

We used WCAA data to assess daily temporal patterns in snowy owl observations and captures. We visualized temporal patterns using density plots, producing one plot for all observations and another for successful captures. We estimated daily activity and captured peaks by applying a kernel density estimator to the distribution of recorded observation times and identifying local maxima in the smoothed curve. We then ranked these maxima by height and retained the two highest values as the primary activity periods, using them as indices for peak snowy owl activity.

Time-of-year analysis

To evaluate seasonal patterns in snowy owl activity, we used WCAA snowy owl data and standardized all dates to support consistent ordering and comparison across years. We began by parsing each observation's month-day field and assigning it a placeholder year (2000), creating a uniform date structure suitable for chronological analyses. We next calculated a fiscal day-of-year index that began on 1 September to align with the biologically relevant migration-period calendar (as defined in the methods above). Under this framework, 1 September was assigned as day 1, and days progressed sequentially through 31 August. We visualized the resulting seasonal distribution using kernel density plots based on the fiscal day-of-year index. To complement this, we generated boxplots depicting activity across all winters combined and within each migration period individually. For clearer interpretation, we converted all fiscal-day values to their approximate calendar-date equivalents.

Migration timing

To compare interannual shifts in migration timing and identify broader patterns across migration periods, we calculated summary statistics for each period describing activity timing, including the minimum and maximum dates of snowy owl observations. To evaluate overall patterns across years, we also summarized timing across all migration periods by calculating average start and end dates. For clearer interpretation, all fiscal-day values (as defined in the methods above) were converted to their approximate calendar-date equivalents and visualized in migration-window plots.

Snowy owl-aircraft interactions

To assess the risk and spatial distribution of snowy owl-aircraft collisions (i.e., strikes), we summarized strike data from the FAA's National Wildlife Strike Database (retrieved 24 October 2025; NWSD 2025). We summarized strike metrics by airport, including total strikes and the number of damaging strikes (i.e., records indicating

damage), and compared these counts among airports. Finally, we summarized strike metrics by migration period for DTW and for all other airports combined to provide context for comparison.

Spatial analysis

To estimate high-use areas by snowy owls, we used WCAA data and conducted broad spatial analyses. At the time of this study, DTW was divided into 22 Wildlife Management Zones delineated by prominent landmarks (e.g., roads, runways) and habitat types. Accordingly, we performed all spatial analyses at the Management Zone level. We visualized spatial patterns in snowy owl activity in ArcGIS Pro (ESRI 2024) using a choropleth map summarizing the frequency of events within each zone.

Banding and recapture

To estimate the number of unique individuals captured and recaptured, we used WCAA–USDA banding records for DTW (data retrieved 26 November 2025). Due to mismatched reporting timelines, these records were not as up to date as other datasets used in this study; therefore, banding data were limited in 2024 and unavailable for 2025. We summarized the total number of captures and recaptures both overall and by migration period. Birds were classified as recaptured when duplicate band numbers appeared within the dataset or within the same migration period. For within-year assessments, we did not consider individuals captured during different migration periods to be recaptures, as these events did not align with operational management practices and were judged unlikely to reflect management-related return behavior.

To assess how changes in snowy owl management strategies affected recapture rates, we compared two management periods: the early management period, associated with migration periods 2018–2019 and earlier, and the later management period, associated with migration periods 2019–2020 and later. During the early management period, which also encompassed the initial years following DTW’s wildlife program inception in 2016, snowy owls were translocated to nearby state lands located approximately 40 miles from the airport (Euclidean distance). These short-distance translocations incorporated limited habitat considerations and were selected largely for operational efficiency (e.g., staff time and travel distance). However, their effectiveness was later questioned as several individuals returned to DTW following release.

Beginning in winter 2019–2020, DTW implemented updated snowy owl translocation procedures informed by emerging scientific recommendations (e.g., McCabe et al. 2022). The revised approach emphasized release distances of ≥ 100 miles (Euclidean distance) and habitat-based site selection, prioritizing open landscapes with high proportions of

wetland and cropland (including grassland and pasture). Such habitats have been associated with reduced likelihood of snowy owls returning following translocation. We applied this early–late management period classification to evaluate whether the updated translocation procedures corresponded with lower snowy owl recapture rates.

Results and discussion

Capture-method assessment

We evaluated the performance of multiple snowy owl capture methods and found that use varied substantially among techniques (Figure 2). From migration periods 2016–2017 through 2024–2025, we documented 97 successful capture events. The Bal-chatri trap was the most frequently used and most consistently successful capture method, accounting for 37% of captures (Figure 2; see Appendix A for an example of its application). Although pole traps alone accounted for the third-highest number of captures (13%)—and were the second most common active method—they resulted in nearly three times fewer captures than the Bal-chatri. Pole traps were often used in combination with other methods, particularly the Bal-chatri, where they served as an elevated perch to draw owls into the trapping area and help increase capture opportunities.

The Swedish goshawk trap was the second most successful method and the only passive technique used during this period, representing 24% of total captures (Figure 2). Approximately ten Swedish goshawk traps were deployed year-round across the airfield. Their distribution across Wildlife Management Zones allowed for broad spatial coverage and consistent trapping pressure in areas known for high raptor activity, which contributed to their overall effectiveness. Hand-based methods (Hand and Net captures) collectively accounted for 15% of successful events (Figure 2). These techniques required staff to approach birds at close range using hand nets (e.g., muskie net, talon net) or, when safe and appropriate, by hand. Although used opportunistically, these methods were effective when owls were stationary, grounded, or otherwise approachable with minimal risk, and they provided a valuable option for birds that were difficult to capture using other techniques. It is important to note that capture effort varied across methods, staff, and years, and these differences influenced the proportion of captures attributed to each technique. Despite these differences in effort, the results highlight which methods consistently provided reliable outcomes under DTW’s operational conditions.

Figure 2. Percentage of successful snowy owl captures by method at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) during the 2016–2025 migration seasons. The net method included hand and talon nets. Most snowy owls were captured using Bal-chatri traps, although capture effort differed among methods.

Time-of-day analysis

We assessed daily temporal patterns in snowy owl observations and captures and found that snowy owls exhibited a crepuscular activity pattern, with observation and capture peaks aligning relatively close with one another (Figure 3). Of the 722 snowy owl activity records, 99 included time information, including 22 of the 97 successful captures used for this analysis. In Detroit, Michigan, on 16 January (approximate median observation date), sunrise occurred at approximately 07:25 and sunset at 17:09 EST. Activity peaked at 08:50 and 16:49 EST, corresponding to roughly 1.5 hours after sunrise and 20 minutes

before sunset, respectively (Figure 3). Capture times exhibited a similar pattern, peaking after sunrise and before sunset (10:40 and 16:07 EST, respectively; Figure 3).

However, we found that morning capture times lagged the morning observation peak, which may reflect the additional time required for observation, notification, and trap setup before a capture attempt can occur. In contrast, evening captures occurred slightly before the evening observation peak, suggesting that evening staff may be better positioned to prepare equipment and respond ahead of the highest-activity period. For example, snowy owls observed earlier in the day may allow staff to stage equipment in advance of the evening activity window, improving capture efficiency. Although our dataset was limited (22 capture records with time data), our results suggest that successful captures at DTW may be slightly skewed toward the late afternoon period. However, capture success rates are generally considered highest in the early morning, just before or at daybreak, when owls typically take a final meal before roosting (personal communication, T. McDonald, Project SNOWstorm). Collectively, our findings highlight the operational value of maintaining Wildlife Division coverage during morning and evening hours, as well as the importance of timely communication of snowy owl observations among staff and departments—as prompt reporting supports faster response times and contributes to safer airfield operations. In these situations, enhanced outreach, education, and internal media can further support effective reporting and awareness (see Appendix B for an example of outreach materials).

Figure 3. Density of (a) snowy owl observations and (b) successful snowy owl captures at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport during migration periods 2016–2025. Vertical dashed lines mark peak activity times, identified as the two highest local maxima from a kernel density estimator and used as indices of peak snowy owl activity. Snowy owls exhibited a crepuscular activity pattern, with observation and capture peaks occurring in close temporal proximity. For reference, on 16 January—the median observation date—sunrise in Detroit, Michigan occurred at approximately 07:25 and sunset at 17:09 EST.

Time-of-year analysis

We used WCAA's observational and capture data as an index to evaluate seasonal patterns of snowy owl activity and found that activity peaked in late December and early February (Figure 4). In general, activity increased quicker from the first observation to the December peak than it did declining from the February peak until the last observation—suggesting they arrive much quicker than they leave (Figure 4). Similarly, most activity occurred between December and February, including a median activity date of January 18th (IQR = December 20th – February 19th; Figure 5)—an important time when snowy owl–aircraft hazard risk is likely at its highest. We also evaluated snowy owl activity by migration period and found that activity varied widely among migration periods, from only a few records within a month to extended activity lasting up to six months (Figure 6). We found that the highest activity occurred during 2017–2018, likely reflecting a continental snowy owl irruption linked to high breeding success in the previous season. Notably, the migration period of 2023–2024 was the only one of the nine migration periods in this study to have zero snowy owl observations at DTW.

Although 2023–2024 lacked any local observations, the absence of detections at a single site does not necessarily indicate a broader regional change. Snowy owls are nomadic, irruptive predators whose winter abundance at temperate latitudes tracks pulsed lemming resources on Arctic breeding grounds, producing strong interannual variability in both regional numbers and local site use (Therrien et al. 2014; Robillard et al. 2016; Therrien et al. 2017, 2021; McCabe et al. 2023). Consequently, highly variable winter movements—including the choice of alternate inland, agricultural, or coastal habitats—mean that some years will produce no detections at individual locations like DTW, even when snowy owls remain present elsewhere in the region.

Similar to variability in activity levels among migration periods, we also observed substantial interannual shifts in migration timing and duration (Figure 7). Across migration periods 2016–2025, snowy owls arrived on average on 25 November (95% CI: 7 November–12 December) and departed on 4 March (95% CI: 3 February–3 April; Figure 7). The narrower confidence interval around arrival suggests that arrival timing is more predictable than departure timing, which varied by nearly two months. The earliest documented arrival at DTW occurred on 26 October, and the latest observation occurred on 29 April, representing the extreme bounds of snowy owl presence during the study period (Figure 7). Migration duration averaged 99 days (95% CI: 56–142 days), ranging from a minimum of 5 days—likely representing a single short-stay individual—to a maximum of 174 days during the highly active 2017–2018 period (Figures 6 and 7). Migration periods with arrival dates earlier than the 25 November average were frequently linked to increased snowy owl

activity and longer migration durations (Figure 7), suggesting early arrival timing may serve as a predictive indicator. Collectively, these results illustrate the high interannual variability in snowy owl migration behavior and highlight the importance of preparing for both early arrivals and prolonged seasonal presence.

Figure 4. Density of snowy owl activity at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport during Migration Periods 2016–2025. We aggregated snowy owl observations and captures to serve as an index of overall activity. Activity showed two general peaks, occurring in late December and again in early February.

Figure 5. Snowy owl activity at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport during migration periods 2016–2025. We aggregated snowy owl observations and captures to index overall activity. The light-blue box represents the interquartile range (IQR; 25th–75th percentiles), and the vertical purple line marks the median date. Blue points represent individual records. Whiskers extend to the minimum and maximum values. Most activity occurred between December and February, a period when snowy owl–aircraft hazard risk is likely greatest.

Figure 6. Snowy owl activity at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport by migration periods 2016–2017 through 2024–2025. We combined snowy owl observations and captures to index activity. Light-blue boxes indicate the interquartile range (25th–75th percentiles), purple lines mark medians, blue points show individual records, and whiskers extend to the minimum and maximum values. Activity varied widely among migration periods, from only a few records within a month to extended activity lasting up to six months. The highest activity occurred during 2017–2018, likely reflecting a continental snowy owl irruption linked to high breeding success. Also note that there was a local absence of snowy owl activity at DTW during the 2023–2024 migration period.

Figure 7. Migration-period windows at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport during migration periods 2016–2025. Green points on the left indicate snowy owl arrival dates (first observation of the season), and red points on the right indicate the end of the migration period (final observation of the season). The vertical dashed green line on the left represents the average arrival date, and the vertical dashed red line on the right represents the average departure date. Migration timing and duration varied among migration periods. Migration periods with arrival dates earlier than average (25 November) were often associated with higher snowy owl activity and longer migration durations.

Snowy owl-aircraft interactions

Between the 2016–2017 and 2024–2025 migration periods, 179 snowy owl strikes were reported to the FAA nationwide, and DTW accounted for 12% (n = 22) of all incidents. We found that DTW recorded the second-highest number of snowy owl strikes in the country, surpassed only by Logan International Airport in Massachusetts (n = 37; Table 1). Notably, DTW also reported the highest number of damaging snowy owl strikes, responsible for 27% (n = 4) of all such events nationwide (Table 1). Further, recent analysis identified snowy owls as the most hazardous bird species at DTW (Gurney et al. 2025; Table 2). This contrasts sharply with national assessments by DeVault et al. (2011) and Ross et al. (2025), who ranked snowy owls 24th and 25th nationwide, respectively. Together, these comparisons illustrate that wildlife–aircraft risk is highly airport-specific; species posing relatively low hazard nationally may still represent significant operational risks at individual airports.

The 2017–2018 migration period was particularly impactful at DTW, accounting for 73% (n = 16) of the airport’s snowy owl strikes and 50% (n = 2) of its damaging strikes (Figure 8). Consistent with several of our other findings, this spike likely reflects a snowy owl irruption—an irregular, large-scale movement driven by exceptionally high reproductive output during the preceding breeding season (Robillard et al. 2016; Curk et al. 2018). National strike totals mirrored this pattern: snowy owl strikes across all U.S. airports also peaked during 2017–2018 (Figure 8), suggesting that irruptive winters elevate snowy owl activity at airports and, in turn, increase strike rates.

Importantly, DTW has not recorded a snowy owl strike in the past five years (Figure 8). Several factors may explain this decline. One possibility is reduced snowy owl presence in recent winters, consistent with broader indications of worldwide decreases in breeding populations (McCabe et al. 2024). Another likely contributor is the continued growth and professionalization of DTW’s wildlife program. Beginning around 2020, we implemented updated translocation strategies aligned with recommendations from McCabe et al. (2022) to reduce owl return rates—an issue more common during earlier years of DTW’s snowy owl management efforts. In recent winters, owls were released much farther from the airport in landscapes dominated by open habitat and higher proportions of wetland and cropland (including grasslands and pasture), conditions associated with lower likelihood of return (McCabe et al. 2022). This multi-faceted approach may help to “un-spring” the ecological trap that airport environments often present for snowy owls.

Willow Run Airport, located roughly six miles from DTW, also ranked among the top ten airports nationwide for snowy owl strikes, with four documented incidents (Table 2). Collectively, these findings underscore that the broader DTW region functions as a key

concentration area for snowy owls and a national hot spot for snowy owl–aircraft collisions. More broadly, many of the top-ranked airports for snowy owl strikes are located in the Midwest, reinforcing the importance of the Great Lakes region as an important wintering area for this species (McCabe et al. 2021).

Given the elevated regional risk of snowy owls at DTW, we recommend a zero-tolerance, all-hands-on-deck approach for immediate management action (e.g., capture and translocation) whenever a snowy owl is detected at the airport—or whenever top-ranked hazardous species are detected at any airport. Anecdotal evidence suggests that the longer an individual snowy owl remains within an airport environment, the more habituated it becomes, potentially reducing the effectiveness of management interventions. Rapid response is therefore essential for minimizing strike risk and maintaining aviation safety. These results also highlight the importance of timely communication among staff—both within the Wildlife Division and across departments—to ensure that snowy owl observations are reported and addressed without delay.

Table 1. Results from Gurney et al. (2025) based on the at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport 2016–2024 wildlife–aircraft strike dataset. These values were used to generate composite rankings that quantify and compare the relative hazard level of wildlife species to aircraft operations. Snowy owls were identified as the most hazardous species at DTW.

Species	% of strikes with damage	% of strikes with substantial damage	% of strikes with effect on flight	Composite rank
Snowy owl (<i>Bubo scandiacus</i>)	18	9	14	1
Turkey vulture (<i>Cathartes aura</i>)	50	50	0	2
Double-crested cormorant (<i>Phalacrocorax auritis</i>)	50	0	0	3
Gulls (<i>Larus sp.</i>)	7	2	8	4
Canada goose (<i>Branta canadensis</i>)	17	0	0	5
Red-tailed hawk (<i>Buteo jamaicensis</i>)	7	0	4	6
Rough-legged hawk (<i>Buteo lagopus</i>)	12	0	0	6
Coyote (<i>Canis latrans</i>)	0	0	33	6
Mallard (<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>)	10	0	0	9
European starling (<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>)	3	0	3	10

Table 2. Snowy owl–aircraft strikes and damaging strikes by U.S. airport during migration periods 2016–2025. Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport ranked second nationwide in total snowy owl strikes and first in damaging snowy owl strikes.

Airport	Strikes	Damaging strikes
GENERAL EDWARD LAWRENCE LOGAN INTL ARPT	37	3
DETROIT METRO WAYNE COUNTY ARPT	22	4
CHICAGO O'HARE INTL ARPT	21	0
JOHN F KENNEDY INTL	15	1
CHICAGO MIDWAY INTL ARPT	8	0
MINNEAPOLIS-ST PAUL INTL/WOLD-CHAMBERLAIN ARPT	8	1
CLEVELAND-HOPKINS INTL ARPT	7	0
UNKNOWN	6	3
GENERAL MITCHELL INTL	4	0
NEWARK LIBERTY INTL ARPT	4	0
WILLOW RUN ARPT	4	0
BUFFALO-NIAGARA INTL	3	0
LA GUARDIA ARPT	3	0
PORTLAND INTL JETPORT (ME)	3	0
ALBANY INTL	2	0
BRADLEY INTL	2	0
CHERRY CAPITAL ARPT	2	0
GREATER ROCHESTER INTL	2	0
KANSAS CITY INTL	2	0
OUTAGAMIE COUNTY REGIONAL	2	2
QUONSET STATE ARPT	2	0
RONALD REAGAN WASHINGTON NATIONAL ARPT	2	0
ANOKA COUNTY-BLAINE	1	0
BALTIMORE/WASH INTL THURGOOD MARSHAL ARPT	1	0
GERALD R. FORD INTL ARPT	1	0
HECTOR INTERNATIONAL	1	0
INDIANAPOLIS INTL ARPT	1	0
JAMES M COX DAYTON INTL	1	0
JOE FOSS FIELD ARPT	1	0
JOHN GLENN COLUMBUS INTL ARPT	1	0
KALAMAZOO/BATTLE CREEK INTL	1	0
LA CROSSE MUNICIPAL AIRPORT	1	0
MUHAMMAD ALI INTERNATIONAL	1	0
NANTUCKET MEMORIAL	1	0
NIAGARA FALLS INTL	1	0
PITTSBURGH INTL ARPT	1	0
STEWART INTL AIRPORT	1	0
THE EASTERN IOWA ARPT	1	1
TORONTO/LESTER B. PEARSON INTL	1	0
WILLISTON BASIN INTL AIRPORT	1	0

Figure 8. Number of snowy owl strikes nationwide and at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) by migration period, 2016–2017 through 2024–2025. DTW exhibited elevated strike activity during nationally high-impact years, including the 2017–2018 irruption, but has had no snowy owl strikes in more recent migration periods, suggesting both changing owl occurrence and more effective local management.

Spatial analysis

Using snowy owl observations as an index of space use, we found that snowy owls disproportionately used the northern portions of the airport (Figure 9). The northeasternmost corner of DTW (Wildlife Management Zone 12) accounted for the highest frequency of snowy owl observations, representing 26% of all spatially explicit records (175 of 664). This area contained a relatively large expanse of open land cover and a high density of perching structures, including numerous light poles associated with rental car facilities (Figure A1)—which served as the core concentration area of observations (Figure 10). The northwesternmost portion of the airfield (Wildlife Management Zone 1) represented the second highest concentration of snowy owl activity, with 86 observations (13%), approximately half that of the most active zone (Figure 9). An adjacent northwestern area (Wildlife Management Zone 5) accounted for an additional 59 observations (9%; Figure 9). The combined northwesternmost region (Wildlife Management Zones 1 and 5) similarly contained extensive open land cover and a high density of perching sites, including offices, warehouses, fuel tanks, and other storage facilities—with activity concentrating in these areas along the border between zones (Figure 11).

Most snowy owl strikes occurred on runways extending into these northern zones, particularly Runways 4R/22L and 3L/21R, while damaging strikes were distributed relatively evenly across runways where strikes were recorded (Table 3). These results highlight the importance of these high-use northern areas in contributing to strike risk on associated runways. They also underscore the need for enhanced surveillance in these zones throughout the broader snowy owl migration period (26 October–29 April; Figure 7), with additional attention during daily and seasonal activity peaks (Figure 3 and Figure 4). Not surprisingly, no strikes were recorded on the crosswind runways (9L/27R or 9R/27L), likely reflecting their lower operational use combined with the observed northern-heavy space-use patterns of snowy owls at DTW (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Frequency of snowy owl observation records at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport during the 2016–2025 migration periods. The northeastern corner of the airfield contained the highest concentration of snowy owl records, with elevated observations occurring across the broader northern region.

Figure 10. Northeasternmost area of Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport associated with the highest frequency of snowy owl observations during the 2016–2025 migration periods. Dark red fill and borders indicate the general boundaries of Wildlife Management Zone 12, and the black circle marks the core concentration of observations. This area contained a relatively large expanse of open land cover and a high density of perching structures, including numerous light poles associated with rental car facilities.

Figure 11. Northwesternmost area of Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport associated with the second-highest frequency of snowy owl observations during the 2016–2025 migration periods. Orange fill and borders indicate the general boundaries of the combined Wildlife Management Zones 1 and 5. The black circle marks the core concentration of snowy owl observations along the border between these two zones. This area contained a relatively large expanse of open land cover and a high density of perching structures, including numerous infrastructure buildings such as offices, warehouses, fuel tanks, and storage facilities.

Table 3. Snowy owl strike and damaging-strike records by runway at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport during Migration Periods 2016–2025. Most strikes occurred on Runways 4R/22L and 3L/21R, while damaging strikes were distributed relatively evenly across runways where strikes occurred. No strikes were recorded on either crosswind runway (9L/27R or 9R/27L).

Runway	Number of strike records	Number of damaging-strike records
4R/22L	10	1
3L/21R	9	1
3R/21L	2	1
4L/22R	1	1
9L/27R	0	0
9R/27L	0	0

Banding and recaptures

We found that snowy owl recapture rates at DTW were relatively low across migration periods, with only 14% of banded individuals recaptured. Our WCAA–USDA banding records included 98 total capture events representing 84 unique individuals, resulting in 14 recapture events associated with 8 individual snowy owls. Notably, this 14% return rate across migration periods reflects only snowy owls originally banded at DTW that were detected and subsequently recaptured upon returning to the airport, rather than all DTW-banded individuals that may have revisited undetected.

Because our return rate was calculated across all migration periods, an individual could be recaptured during a different period than the one in which it was originally captured. This broad, cross-period calculation may obscure insights into management effectiveness within any single migration period, each of which exhibited its own recapture rate. For instance, most migration periods in our dataset had a 0% recapture rate, whereas the irruptive 2017–2018 migration period showed the highest within-period recapture rate at 14% and accounted for 8 of the 10 within-period recapture events. These events involved 5 individual snowy owls, including one bird that was captured four times (i.e., recaptured three times) within the 2017–2018 migration period.

Across all migration periods, 13 of the 14 total recapture events involved birds originally banded during the irruptive 2017–2018 migration period—the only exception being a bird captured in 2019–2020 and relocated approximately 40 miles away with limited

consideration of habitat characteristics (e.g., land-cover composition). Together, these patterns suggest that irruptive migration dynamics were a strong driver of snowy owl returns at DTW. Three individuals were captured across multiple migration periods: one snowy owl across three periods (initial capture plus two multi-migration-period recaptures) and two others across two periods. All multi-migration-period recapture events involved birds banded during the irruptive 2017–2018 cohort, reinforcing the conclusion that irruptive winters are important drivers of snowy owl return rates and play a key role in cross-period return patterns.

For comparison, McCabe et al. (2022) reported that approximately 33% of telemetry-tracked snowy owls returned to airports following initial capture during an overwintering period. If we applied their approach and excluded multiple translocations of the same individual within a migration period—our maximum individual-based return rate would be 16% for the 2017–2018 migration period. Given DTW’s rapid response and high capture probability, it is reasonable that our recapture estimates would be lower—or at most comparable—to the telemetry-based return rates reported by McCabe et al. (2022). Although some birds may return undetected, the most important operational outcome is that high-risk individuals are detected quickly and removed from DTW, thereby reducing the likelihood of hazardous wildlife–aircraft interactions.

It is important to note that we had the unique opportunity to collaborate with Project SNOWstorm, a snowy owl research initiative that provided us with additional insight into snowy owl movement and return behavior. Between 2019 and 2022, three snowy owls at DTW were fitted with backpack transmitters that contributed to the telemetry dataset used by McCabe et al. (2022). Of these three individuals, two (Buckeye and Wolverine) returned to DTW but were not recaptured, while the third bird—released more than 100 miles from the airport near Saginaw Bay in a landscape dominated by suitable open-habitat cover—did not return. Observations from these telemetry-tagged individuals further reinforced the importance of translocation strategy, particularly the value of long-distance, habitat-based release sites, in preventing snowy owls from returning to the airfield. These findings directly informed DTW’s later snowy owl management approach adopted in winter 2019–2020.

We estimated a 75% reduction in snowy owl recaptures between early (migration periods 2018–2019 and earlier) and later (2019–2020 and after) management periods at DTW, suggesting increasingly effective management over time. Early in the program, snowy owl translocations were generally short-distance (~40 miles), whereas later years emphasized long-distance (≥ 100 miles), habitat-based release strategies. Although snowy owl activity indices were generally lower in recent years (Figure 6), the shift to long-distance, habitat-based translocations corresponded with substantially lower recapture

rates (Table 4). Beginning around 2019, DTW also implemented targeted small-mammal management, including rodenticide treatments in areas where small-mammal indices exceeded operational thresholds. Because long-distance translocation and small-mammal suppression were first implemented during similar years, it is difficult to fully disentangle their respective effects. In addition, natural year-to-year variation in snowy owl irruptive migration patterns adds further ecological complexity. Importantly, the later management period was associated with zero snowy owl–aircraft collisions (Figure 8). This distinction is notable because the 2021–2022 migration period coincided with a secondary nationwide peak in snowy owl strikes, indicative of another irruptive or high-activity winter. Although localized absences of owls during irruptive years are possible, these patterns more likely reflect rapid and highly effective response efforts by Wildlife Division staff. Taken together, the relative stability of return rates in other raptors (e.g., red-tailed hawks) and the recent absence of snowy owl strikes suggest that capture and translocation strategies played a more influential role than small-mammal suppression in reducing snowy owl recaptures at DTW.

Overall, DTW’s evolving snowy owl management program aligned with broader wildlife hazard management literature emphasizing multi-faceted, long-term strategies (Schwartz et al. 2014, Altringer et al. 2024). Integrated approaches are widely recommended when multiple ecological and operational factors influence wildlife presence at airports—like those at DTW (Schwartz et al. 2014). Long-term planning is similarly critical; such programs build institutional knowledge, improve adaptability, and enhance the cost-effectiveness of wildlife hazard mitigation. Altringer et al. (2024), for example, demonstrated that proactive, long-term airport wildlife programs can yield benefit–cost ratios exceeding 7:1, primarily through reductions in strike-related expenses. Altogether, our results support a proactive, integrated, and long-term management approach for snowy owls at DTW. The combined evidence from our banding data, management history, and the broader literature indicates that DTW’s evolving strategy—incorporating long-distance translocations, habitat-based release sites, and small-mammal management—is ecologically sound, operationally effective, and economically justified.

Table 4. Snowy owl capture events, number of unique snowy owls caught, total recapture events, recapture rate, and recapture rate of unique birds at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport by migration period.

Migration period	Total capture events	Unique birds	Total recapture events	Recapture rate	Unique recapture rate
2016-2017	1	1	0	0.0000	0.0000
2017-2018	59	51	8	0.1356	0.1569
2018-2019	8	7	1	0.1250	0.1429
2019-2020	9	8	1	0.1111	0.1250
2020-2021	5	5	0	0.0000	0.0000
2021-2022	15	15	0	0.0000	0.0000
2024-2025	1	1	0	0.0000	0.0000

We recognize that our results were derived from historical data, reflecting past patterns rather than real-time risks. As snowy owl populations, behavior, and surrounding land use continues to change, we acknowledge that ongoing monitoring and adaptive management may be necessary to identify and address emerging wildlife hazards. Other limitations of this study included the use of non-standardized surveys, variation in trapping effort, imperfect detection, and small sample sizes in some analyses. Many of these limitations reflected the need to balance competing, time-sensitive, and often unpredictable work obligations—such as responding to wildlife-aircraft strikes or addressing immediate hazards near runways. Despite these constraints, we uncovered consistent patterns that carry meaningful implications for wildlife management and aviation safety—locally at DTW and across the broader airport system.

Ethics statement

This research acknowledges the ethical considerations involved in the management and handling of wildlife at airports. All wildlife management activities referenced in this study were conducted under appropriate federal and state permits, including those issued by relevant federal and state wildlife agencies. These actions were carried out in accordance with established legal and ethical guidelines and were aimed at protecting human life and ensuring aviation safety by mitigating the risk of wildlife-aircraft strikes. Our research does not endorse unnecessary harm to wildlife and supports the use of non-lethal methods whenever feasible. Ethical wildlife management practices, including habitat modification and deterrence, are emphasized as primary strategies, with direct control considered only as a last resort and in full regulatory compliance.

Data availability

The R code used for main analyses in this study are available at the GitHub repository: https://github.com/Steven-M-Gurney/Snowy_Owl_Behavior. Note that some data used in this study were sensitive and therefore were not made available with the R code. These internal data were housed with the Wildlife Division's Special Publications database.

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Appendix A: Bal-chatri capture method

Content adapted from materials provided by N. Scobal, Wildlife Biologist, USDA – Wildlife Services

Modified Bal-chatri traps consist of a lure cage stocked with suitable lure birds (e.g., rock pigeons [*Columba livia*], European starlings [*Sturnus vulgaris*]), 4–6 padded foothold traps (with modified, lower-tension springs), and one or more rebar T-stakes for stabilization (Figure A1). For effective deployment, the trap array should be positioned approximately 50–100 yards from the owl, ensuring a clear line of sight to the lure cage. A simple field check is to crouch to the height of the lure cage—if the owl is visible from that position, the lure cage will also be visible to the owl. To prevent the owl from observing trap setup, consider positioning the truck to block its line of sight. At the same time, be mindful that vehicle movement can spook an owl, including passing airfield staff or headlights. Communicating to keep the area clear of vehicles during active trapping can help reduce disturbance and improve trapping success.

Securing the lure cage with at least two rebar T-stakes prevents it from being tipped or dragged during an owl's approach. Foothold traps should be arranged both around and on top of the lure cage at varying distances to maximize capture opportunities. Lightly covering the foothold traps with grass or similar natural material helps obscure them without compromising their function. Because snowy owls often land directly on top of the lure cage, placing one or two foothold traps on the cage itself is recommended (Figure A1). These can be stabilized by threading the trap's lever through the wire mesh or by using a loose zip-tie attachment point to support the trap—taking care not to secure the trap to the cage, which would impede proper operation.

Owls frequently approach the lure on foot and may circle it at varying distances. To accommodate this behavior, foothold traps should be positioned both close to the lure (approximately 2–3 inches) and farther out (up to 1–2 feet; Figure A2). Continuous monitoring of the trap array is critical to ensure that captured owls remain in foothold traps for the shortest time possible. Monitoring should occur from a significant distance—typically 100 yards or more—to avoid altering the owl's behavior. Because captures often take place in low-light conditions, binoculars or a thermal-optics unit are valuable tools for effective observation. Once an owl is captured, it should be removed from the foothold trap promptly to minimize the risk of leg abrasions caused by pulling against the trap or tether. Proper protective gloves should always be worn to prevent punctures or bites during handling.

Figure A1. Example of a modified Bal-chatri trap array showing (a) the full trap setup and (b) a successful snowy owl capture using the same method. In panel (a), the trap array includes a lure cage with pigeons and six tethered foothold traps with padded jaws anchored by railroad spikes. Yellow arrows indicate two camouflaged foothold traps and the wire tether line connected to the anchor. Panel (b) shows a snowy owl that approached on foot and was captured while circling the lure cage. This area of the airport was associated with the highest snowy owl activity and contained a relatively large expanse of open land cover and a high density of perching structures, including numerous light poles associated with rental car facilities—visible in the background of panel (a).

Figure A2. Layout of a modified Bal-chatri trap array showing foothold traps placed at variable distances around the lure cage, on the ground. Although not depicted, placing 1–2 foothold traps on top of the lure cage are also recommended.

Appendix B: Outreach materials

Figure B1. Example of outreach material used at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport—developed in response to findings emphasizing the importance of rapid communication among staff. Materials like this poster were used to increase awareness, encourage prompt reporting, and support faster Wildlife Division response to snowy owl hazards.